

Studies in the Rearrangement of Spiranes : Part III—Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-Spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) and its 7-Methyl Derivative and their Rearrangement on Catalytic Dehydrogenation¹

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The spiranes 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethyl cyclopentane) (II, R = H) and its 7-methyl derivative (II, R = CH₃) have been synthesised. When heated with 10% Pd-C, they underwent rearrangement yielding 1,2-dimethyl- and 1,2,6-trimethylphenanthrene respectively. The spiranes have been prepared by the AlCl₃-catalysed condensation of the anhydride of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (III) with benzene and toluene. The resulting keto-acids on catalytic reduction under mild pressure followed by cyclisation and reduction afforded the desired spiranes.

THE spiranes are known to undergo ring transformation on dehydrogenation with selenium². Sengupta and Chatterjee³ synthesised a large number of spiranes of the type 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spirocyclopentane (I) with alkyl substituents in the 2'-position of the spirocyclopentane ring with a view to studying their rearrangement on catalytic dehydrogenation and observed that the substituted spiranes undergo smooth ring transformation on catalytic dehydrogenation giving either phenanthrene derivatives or pyrene derivatives depending on the nature of the alkyl groups. The methyl substituted spiranes of the type I (R = CH₃) were found to undergo ring fission in the spirocyclopentane ring away from the methyl group *i.e.*, between C₁' and C₅' followed by preferential angular cyclisation of the 4-carbon chain resulting in the formation of hydrophenanthrene systems which on dehydrogenation yielded 1-methyl phenanthrene derivatives. On the other hand, ethyl or propyl or *n*-butyl substituted spiranes of the type I (R = C₂H₅ or C₃H₇ or C₄H₉) were found by Chatterjee⁴ to undergo ring fission near the heavy group (between C₁' and C₂') and cyclisation with C₁ giving 4-alkylphenanthrene derivatives which under the condition of catalytic dehydrogenation underwent cyclodehydrogenation forming additional ring and giving pyrene derivatives. Sengupta and Chatterjee further showed that the methyl group in the 3'-position of the spirocyclopentane ring in a spirane of the type (I) effects ring fission in either of the possible ways giving a mixture of 2-methyl and 3-methyl phenanthrenes.

Thus in view of the earlier observation that a specific mode of ring fission in a spirane requires a specific group in a specific position, it would be quite

interesting to study the catalytic dehydrogenation of the spiranes of the type I with different alkyl substituents in the 2'- and 3'-positions. The synthesis of a large number of such disubstituted spiranes and a thorough study of their ring transformation under conditions of catalytic dehydrogenation will throw light on the mechanism of such ring transformation. Moreover, it would be a route to the synthesis of many interesting complex polysubstituted polycyclic compounds. With this end in view, the synthesis of a number of disubstituted spiranes of the type 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (II) have been achieved by an adoption of the method developed earlier and their ring transformations on dehydrogenation have been studied.

The starting material for the synthesis has been *trans* 2,3-dimethyl cyclopentanone prepared from ethyl laevulinate by condensation with ethylmagnesium iodide and heating the resulting lactone with polyphosphoric acid followed by the catalytic reduction of the cyclopentene derivative, by a modification of the method due to Varech *et al.*⁵

Condensation of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentanone with ethylcyanoacetate according to the Cope's method gave ethyl 2,3-dimethylcyclopentylidene cyanoacetate in 88% yield. Treatment of the unsaturated nitrile with potassium cyanide in aqueous alcoholic solution followed by hydrolysis of the resulting dicyanoester furnished, 2,3-dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (III) in 85% overall yield.

The aluminium chloride-catalysed condensation of the anhydride of (III) with benzene gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(2,3-dimethylcyclopentane)- β -benzoyl propionic acid (IV,

R = H) which readily formed a pyrilium salt showing the presence of a keto-methylene grouping⁶. Attempted reduction of the keto-acid by the Clemmensen method led to the formation of a large amount of a neutral high melting product showing an intense I.R. peak at $5.65\ \mu$ and believed to be a bimolecular lactone, which has not been further investigated. The keto acid was however reduced in excellent yield by catalytic method in a Paar apparatus to α -(2,3-dimethylcyclopentane)- γ -phenylbutyric acid which on polyphosphoric acid cyclisation yielded 1-keto-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (V, R = H) in 88% yield.

On reduction by the Clemmensen method, which was somewhat sluggish, the spiroketone afforded the desired spirane (II, R = H). This on dehydrogenation with 10% palladium-on-charcoal underwent smooth ring transformation without any loss of carbon atom giving 1,2-dimethylphenanthrene as the exclusive product which also resulted during the dehydrogenation of the spiroalcohol formed by LiAlH_4 reduction of the ketone V (R = H).

In a similar manner 7-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (II, R = CH_3) was synthesised starting from toluene and the anhydride of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (III). The spirohydrocarbon (II, R = CH_3) when heated with 10% palladium-on-charcoal underwent cyclopentane ring fission as in the previous manner away from the substitution followed by dehydrogenation giving 1,2,6-trimethylphenanthrene which also resulted during the catalytic dehydrogenation of the secondary alcohol formed by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the spiroketone (V, R = CH_3).

Our findings on the rearrangement of spiranes of the type 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (II) during catalytic dehydrogenation are in line with the observations of Sengupta and Chatterjee³ with regard to the dehydrogenation of similar spiranes with a methyl substituent in the 2'-position of the spirocyclopentane ring. The additional methyl group in the 3'-position does not seem to have any effect on the mode of ring fission

and it is not eliminated during dehydrogenation. One thing has emerged clear as a result of our work that the hexahydrophenanthrene derivative (B) likely to be produced by the dehydrogenation and consequent rearrangement of the secondary alcohol (A) in the presence of acidic catalyst, yielded phenanthrene derivatives identical with those obtained from the rearrangement of spiranes suggesting that the ring transformation may take place in both the cases by the Wagner-Meerwein type of rearrangement of the carbon skeleton. Failure of the more nucleophilic C_2-C_1' bond to migrate to C_1 may be due to the interference of the methyl groups in the transition state with the peri hydrogen of naphthalene system. The effect of heavy groups on the dehydrogenation of disubstituted spiranes will throw more light on the mechanism on which work is in progress.

Experimental

All m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected, U.V. spectra were recorded in 95% ethanol in Unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 500. I.R. spectra were recorded in Unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 200G., Petroleum ether used had b.p. $60^\circ=80^\circ$.

(±) trans 2,3-Dimethylcyclopentanone was prepared by a modification of the method of Deniel Varch *et-al.*⁵ starting from ethyl leavulinase. It had b.p. 152° under ordinary pressure. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol as orange plates, m.p. $162^\circ-163^\circ$. (Found : N, 19.21; $C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 19.11). The semicarbazone crystallised from ethanol as fine plates, m.p. 212° . (Found : N, 25.12, $C_8H_{15}N_3O$ requires N, 24.84).

Ethyl 2,3-Dimethylcyclopentylidene cyanoacetate : A solution containing 2,3-dimethyl cyclopentanone (40 g.), ethylcyanoacetate (45 g.), ammonium acetate (7 g.), acetic acid (15 ml.) and benzene (100 ml.) was refluxed in an oil bath at $130^\circ-140^\circ$ for 6 hrs and at $140^\circ-150^\circ$ for 12 hrs., when the separation of water was complete. The mixture was cooled, and diluted with ice-water. The aqueous layer was extracted twice with benzene and the combined organic layer was washed with water. Removal of the solvent and low boiling followed by distillation under reduced pressure afforded the unsaturated nitrile in 88% yield, b.p. $123^\circ-125^\circ$ (1.5 mm), n_{D}^{30} 1.4800 (Found : C, 69.32; H, 7.95; $C_{12}H_{17}NO_2$ requires C, 69.52; H, 8.20).

It absorbed bromine readily in chloroform solution and gave 2,3-dimethyl cyclopentanone on oxidation.

2,3-Dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic Acid (III) : A solution of 36 g. of potassium cyanide in 72 ml. water was added to 50 g. of the foregoing unsaturated nitrile dissolved in 250 ml. of rectified spirit. It was left for a week when the potassium salt separated out. It was decomposed with dil. hydrochloric acid after removal of alcohol. The organic matter was extracted with benzene and washed with water. Removal of benzene followed by distillation gave the dicyanoester, b.p. 125° (1 mm) which was boiled under reflux with 400 ml. (1 : 2) hydrochloric acid for 72 hrs. The acid that separated

on cooling was purified by extraction with hot sodium carbonate soln. to give 45 g. (85.5% based on unsaturated nitrile) of the dicarboxylic acid which after two crystallisations from hot water yielded colourless needles of (III) melting at 160° . (Found : C, 60.13; H, 7.91; $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.00; H, 8.00).

The anhydride of the above acid (III) obtained by heating the acid with excess of acetic anhydride for 2 hrs., was a colourless liquid, b.p. 140° (3 mm). (Found : C, 65.90; H, 7.64; $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.93; H, 7.69).

The anilic acid, crystallised from aqueous ethanol in plates, m.p. 175° (Found : N, 5.15, $C_{16}H_{23}NO_3$ requires N, 5.09).

The anil, prepared by heating the anilic acid at 180° crystallised from aqueous alcohol in needles, m.p. 107° . (Found : N, 5.51; $N_{16}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 5.45).

α -(2,3-Dimethylcyclopentane), β -benzoyl-propionic Acid (IV, R = H) : A solution of 10 g. of the anhydride of the acid (III) in 10 ml dry benzene was added slowly to a well-stirred solution containing 16 g. powdered aluminium chloride in 40 ml. dry benzene at 0 to -5° . After stirring at 0° for 6 hrs., it was kept overnight and then stirred for another 30 mins. at $50^\circ-60^\circ$. The reaction complex was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and the excess benzene was removed by steam distillation. The residue was treated with hot 5% sodium carbonate solution and charcoal, filtered and acidified when 12 g. of the acidic matter was obtained. On crystallisation twice from acetic acid and finally from pet-ethers, 8.5 g. of the ketoacid melting at 107° were obtained as colourless needles. (Found : C, 73.71; H, 7.58; N.E., 257; $C_{16}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.80; H, 7.70; N.E. 260). The 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in light orange yellow needles, m.p. 218° . (Found : N, 12.58; $C_{22}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.72).

The pyrylium salt of the keto acid prepared as described earlier⁴ was a crimson red powder which did not melt upto 290° .

α -(2,3-Dimethylcyclopentane)- γ -phenylbutyric Acid : Six grams of the ketoacid was reduced with hydrogen in a Paar apparatus at 40-45 lbs./P.s.i, pressure and $45^\circ-50^\circ$, in 50 ml. of ethanol containing 400 mg. of 10% palladium-on-charcoal catalyst. It was filtered and distilled under reduced pressure when 5 g. of the acid distilled as a colourless thick liquid, b.p. $170^\circ-180^\circ$ (2.5 mm.). It readily solidified on trituration with pet-ether and crystallised from pet-ether in needles, m.p. 83° . (Found : C, 78.32; H, 9.06; $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.05; H, 8.94).

Reduction of 3 g. of the keto acid (IV, R = H) using 30 g. of amalgamated zinc, 30 ml. of conc. HCl, 1 ml. of toluene and refluxing for 60 hrs. gave 0.4 g. of the reduced acid, m.p. 83° together with 2 g. of the neutral matter which after repeated crystallisations from benzene separated as stout needles, m.p. $257^\circ-258^\circ$. The compound showed an intense I.R. peak—at 5.65μ and is believed to be a lactone formed by bimolecular reduction of the keto-acid.

1-Keto - 1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene - 2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (V, R = H): Five grams of the foregoing reduced acid was cyclised with 60 g. of PPA on a steam bath by thorough mechanical stirring for 1 hr. when an orange coloured complex was formed. It was decomposed with ice, extracted with ether and thoroughly washed with aqueous ammonia. The residue left after removal of the solvent on distillation under reduced pressure gave 4.2 g. of the spiroketone as a colourless thin liquid having a characteristic odour, b.p. 145° (1 mm.), n_D^{30} 1.5508. (Found: C, 83.91; H, 8.68, C₁₆H₂₀O requires C, 84.21, H, 8.77).

It did not form 2,4-D.N.P. derivative possibly owing to steric hindrance. However, it showed a strong I.R. conjugated carbonyl absorption at 5.95 μ and U.V. absorption of a conjugated cyclic ketone, 229 nm (log ϵ 4.10); 248 nm (log ϵ 3.98); 295 nm (log ϵ 3.21).

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydronaphthalene - 2,2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (II, R = H): The spiroketone (V, R = H) (1.7 g.) was gently boiled under reflux with amalgamated zinc (17 g.), conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.), toluene (2 ml.) and acetic acid (2 ml.) for 80 hrs. with occasional addition of conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) after every 20 hrs. The organic matter was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried and distilled to give 1.1 g. of the spirane (II, R = H) which after chromatographic purification through alumina using pet-ether was obtained as a mobile colourless liquid b.p. 120°-125° (1 mm.), n_D^{30} 1.5500. (Found: C, 89.31; H, 10.12; C₁₆H₂₂ requires C, 89.72; H, 10.28).

Dehydrogenation of the spirohydrocarbon (II, R = H): A mixture of 0.8 g. spirane (II, R = H) and 0.1 g. of the 10% palladium-on-charcoal catalyst was heated in a metal bath at 300°-330° for 2 hrs. and at 330°-350° for an additional 1 hr. The mass was extracted with hot benzene and filtered through a short column of alumina. Removal of the solvent followed by distillation afforded 0.4 g. thick liquid which was converted into the picrate in methanol. The separated picrate (0.25 g.) after two crystallisations from methanol was obtained as deep orange fine needles, m.p. 153° (Reported value for the m.p. of the picrate of 1,2-dimethylphenanthrene⁸ is 154°). No other sharp melting product could be isolated from the mother liquor.

The picrate was decomposed by passing a benzene solution of the picrate through alumina. Removal of benzene afforded 0.1 g. of 1,2-dimethyl phenanthrene which crystallised from methanol as light yellow flakes, m.p. 142° (Reported value⁸—142°-3°).

The sym-Trinitrobenzene complex crystallised from ethanol in fine orange needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 9.91; C₂₂H₁₇N₃O₆; requires N, 10.02).

Lithium Aluminium-Hydride Reduction of the spiroketone (V, R = H) and Dehydrogenation of the Alcohol: To a suspension of 0.25 g. of LAH in 25 ml. dry ether, 0.5 g. of the above spiroketone in 25 ml. dry benzene was added. The mixture was

refluxed for 4 hrs. cooled, decomposed with cold dil. sulphuric acid. Usual work up followed by distillation gave 0.4 g. of a clear distillate which when heated with 50 mg. of 10% palladium-on-charcoal for 1 hr at 300°-320° gave 0.2 g. of 1,2-dimethyl phenanthrene as a yellow solid, m.p. 142°.

α -(2,3-Dimethylcyclopentane)- β -(p-toluyloyl)-propionic Acid (IV, R = CH₃): It was prepared from 10 g. of the anhydride of the dicarboxylic acid (III), 40 ml. of dry thiophen free toluene and 15 g. of anhydrous aluminium chloride exactly as in the case of the ketoacid (IV, R = H) when 13 g. of the crude acid matter was obtained. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then from methanol as colourless heavy plates (9.5 g.), m.p. 159° (Found: C, 74.24; H, 7.81; N.E., 272, C₁₇H₂₂O₃ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.03; N.E., 274).

The 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in bright orange plates, m.p. 193° (Found: C, 60.45; H, 5.62, C₂₃H₂₆O₆N₄ requires C, 60.79; H, 5.70). Oxidation of the ketoacid (IV, R = CH₃) by sodium hypobromite gave p-toluic acid, m.p. 181°. The pyrylium salt of the ketoacid was a crimson-red crystalline salt which did not melt upto 290°.

α -(2,3-Dimethylcyclopentane)- γ -(p-tolyl) butyric Acid: Six grams of the ketoacid (IV, R = CH₃), was reduced in a Paar apparatus exactly as described for the reduction of the ketoacid (IV, R = H) to give 5.0 g. of the above reduced acid as a thick colourless liquid, b.p. 180°-182° (0.7 mm.) which solidified on trituration with pet-ether. It crystallised from pet-ether in colourless plates, m.p. 92° (Found: C, 78.18; H, 9.12, C₁₇H₂₄O₂ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23).

1-Keto-7-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (V, R = CH₃): Four grams of the foregoing reduced acid was cyclised with 50 g. of PPA on a steam bath by stirring for 1 hr. as described earlier to give 3.3 g. of the spiroketone (V, R = CH₃), b.p. 150°-153° (1 mm.) as a colourless liquid having a characteristic sweet odour. n_D^{25} 1.5505 (Found: C, 84.11; H, 8.92, C₁₇H₂₂O requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09). The ketone did not form semicarbazone or 2,4-DNP derivative but showed strong I.R. absorption at 5.95 μ and U.V. absorption at 232 nm (log ϵ 4.32); 252 nm (log ϵ 4.14); 295 nm (log ϵ 3.49), characteristic of a conjugated cyclic ketone.

7-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(2',3'-dimethylcyclopentane) (II, R = CH₃): One gram of the ketone (V, R = CH₃) was gently boiled under reflux with amalgamated zinc (10 g.), conc. hydrochloric acid (15 ml.) and toluene (1 ml.) for 80 hrs, exactly as in the preparation of the spirane (II, R = H). Usual work up as described earlier gave the spirane (0.6 g.) as a mobile colourless liquid, b.p. 120°-123° (0.8 mm.); n_D^{25} 1.5365 (Found: C, 89.14; H, 10.24, C₁₇H₂₄ requires C, 89.47; H, 10.53).

Dehydrogenation of the Spirane (II, R = CH₃) with Palladium-on-charcoal: Isolation of 1,2,6-trimethylphenanthrene: The dehydrogenation of 0.4 g. spirane

with 40 mg. of 10% Palladium-on-charcoal as described in the case of the spirane (II, R = H), gave 0.25 g. of a clear liquid which was converted into the picrate in methanolic solution. The separated picrate (0.2 g.) after two crystallisations from ethanol was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 167° (reported value⁹, 167°-168°).

The hydrocarbon regenerated from the picrate yielded, 1,2,6-trimethyl phenanthrene, which crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 127°-128° (reported value⁹, 127°-128°). It shows U.V. absorption at 260 nm (log ϵ 5.14); 304 nm (log ϵ 4.57); 337 nm (log ϵ 3.26); 354 nm (log ϵ 3.31), characteristics of a substituted phenanthrene.

The sym-trinitro benzene complex prepared in ethanolic solution, crystallised from ethanol as fine yellow needles, m.p. 183° (Found : C, 63.81; H, 4.28, C₂₃H₁₉N₃O₆ requires C, 63.97; H, 4.39).

LAH reduction of 1 g. of the spiro-ketone (V, R = CH₃) followed by its dehydration and distillation as described earlier yielded 0.35 g. of 1,2,6-trimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (B, R = CH₃) as a colourless liquid which showed U.V. absorption at 270 nm (log ϵ 3.64) characteristic of a substituted 1,2-dialin¹⁰ and which on dehydrogenation with 10% Pd-C Catalyst gave 1,2,6-trimethylphenanthrene (0.1 g.), m.p. 127°.

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